

Synthesis, characterization, structure and antibacterial activity of di-nuclearalkoxobridged Cu^{II} complex with di-anionic tri-dentate ligand

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Manuscript received 16 July 2018, accepted 20 August 2018

The tri-dentate ONO-donor Schiff base ligand H₂L was produced from the condensation of benzoylacetone and 3-aminopropanol. This tri-dentate alcohol based ligand was treated with Cu(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O to generate two doubly alkoxy bridged di-nuclear copper(II) complex [Cu₂L₂] **1**. Characterization of this compound was carried out by various spectroscopic tools. Compound **1** crystallizes in orthorhombic space group *P2(1)/n* with *a* = 7.322 Å, *b* = 9.938 Å, *c* = 16.137 Å. Single crystal X-ray diffraction study reveals that in di-nuclear copper compound [Cu₂L₂] **1**, both the metal centers adopt a square planar environment and two Cu^{II} centers are bridged by two alkoxy groups. The electronic spectrum of the copper complex shows bands at 422 nm and 550 nm which can be assigned to ²B_{1g}→²A_{1g} and ²B_{1g}→²E_{1g} transitions. The compound shows antibacterial activity. Antibacterial activity of complex **1** was performed by well plate technique. In the above experiment, *V. hydrophila*, *S. aureus* and *B. cereus* were found sensitive to di-nuclear copper(II) complex [Cu₂L₂] **1**.

Keywords: Syntheses, characterization, X-ray structure, electronic spectra, antibacterial activity.

Introduction

Transition metal complexes with Schiff base ligand have remained an important and popular research area due to their simple synthetic procedure and various ranges of applications. Such multidentate chelating ligand can accommodate one, two or more metal ions to produce biologically important metal complexes with aesthetically pleasing structural frame work¹. Binuclear complexes of copper have received much attention due to their relevance to the type 3 copper found in multicopper-containing proteins such as the tyrosinase, hemocyanins and copper oxidases². There are many reports on modelling the copper di-nuclear active sites of these proteins³.

Besides their biological importance, di-nuclear copper compounds exhibit interesting catalytic property as Schiff base ligand can bind transition metals in various oxidation states with unusual structural features. Nowadays, such type of copper complexes with Schiff base ligand have extensively

been used as catalysts for a wide variety of reactions, including olefin polymerization, polymerization of substituted phenols to poly(phenylene ether) (PPE) and oxygen activation^{4,5}.

Transition metal complexes with Schiff base ligands drew significant interest of researchers in the medical science for their immense biological activities⁶. Drug resistance against various pathogens is the major cause of morbidity and mortality throughout the world, so novel antimicrobial drugs play crucial role in biological monitoring of diseases⁷. In recent times, many transition metal complexes with Schiff base ligand have been reported in literature possessing antimicrobial, antibacterial, antifungal, anti-inflammatory and anti-tumor properties⁸. Previously, we reported a series of compounds with phenol based ligand showing antibacterial activity⁹.

Herein, we report synthesis and characterization of a di-nuclear Cu^{II} complexes with tridentate ONO-donor Schiff

base ligand H_2L . X-Ray crystallography, electronic spectroscopy and IR spectroscopy have been carried out to characterize this complex. The new Schiff base ligand and its complex were tested for antibacterial activity against pathogenic bacteria species, such as *V. hydrophila*, *S. aureus* and *B. cereus*.

Experimental

Materials:

Solvents were reagent grade, purified using appropriate drying agents and distilled under prior to their use¹⁰. All other chemicals were reagent grade, commercially available and used as received. Pure culture of the test bacteria were collected from the Microbiology Lab of Vidyasagar University, Medinipur.

Syntheses and characterization:

Ligand:

3-(3-Hydroxypropylimino)-1-phenylbut-1-en-1-ol (H₂L): Benzoylacetone (1.62 g, 10 mmol) was taken in methanol (50 mL). To the methanolic solution about (0.75 g, 10 mmol) 3-amino-1-propanol was added. The solution was put under reflux for 1 h. A yellow color solution was obtained. This yellow solution was cooled at room temperature and kept overnight in open air for crystallization. A yellowish white compound was obtained and it was filtered. The resulting compound was washed with diethyl ether twice (2×10 mL) and finally dried in vacuum.

IR (KBr disk, cm^{-1}): 3416br, 2914s, 2826s, 1587s, 1480s, 1224s, 1023s, 757s, 699s.

ESI-MS in dichloromethane: m/z ($M+H^+$): 220.

Preparation of complex:

[Cu_2L_2] **1**. $Cu(ClO_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (0.180 g, 0.5 mmol) was added to the methanolic solution of ligand H_2L (0.11 g, 0.5 mmol). Few drops of triethyl ammine are mixed and the resulting mixture was stirred. After 1 h stirring, black colored

compound was obtained. It was filtered and washed with methanol. The resulting compound was recrystallized from DCM-MeOH solvent mixture. A black crystalline compound along with single crystals was obtained. Yield: 50%. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{26}H_{30}Cu_2N_2O_4$: C, 55.55; H, 5.34; N, 4.98. Found: C, 54.90 ; H, 5.15; N, 5.10%; IR (KBr disk, cm^{-1}): 3416br, 2919s, 2826br, 1590s, 1570s, 1506s, 1485s, 1280s, 1088s, 753s, 700s, 535s; UV-Vis (MeOH) [λ_{max}/nm ($\epsilon/mol^{-1} cm^2$): 422 (1351), 550 (280).

Fig. 1. Electrospray ionization mass spectrum (ESI-MS positive) of ligand (H_2L) in CH_2Cl_2 .

Scheme 1. Schematic presentation of preparation of ligand.

Physical measurements:

UV-Visible spectra in solution were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 950 UV/VIS/NIR spectrophotometer, while for infrared spectra were employed a Nicolet Magna 750 FT-IR spectrometer, series II with samples prepared as KBr pellets. Mass spectra (ESI-MS in positive ion mode) were recorded on a QTOF Model YA263 Micro Mass Spectrometer.

X-Ray crystallography:

Diffraction quality crystals of **1** were grown at room temperature from DCM-MeOH solvent mixture. Intensity data for the compound was measured on a Bruker SMART 1000 CCD diffractometer using a graphite monochromated MoK_α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) at 293 K. No crystal decay was observed during the data collections. Relevant crystal data and refinement details are given in Table 1. The structures were solved by direct methods and refined on F^2 by a full-matrix

least-squares procedure using the program SHELXL 97^{11,12}.

Results and discussion**Synthesis:**

The di-nuclear copper(II) complex [Cu₂L₂] **1** has been prepared readily by stirring the Cu(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O with the methanolic solution of tri-dentate alcohol based ligand [H₂L] with O, N,O donor set in presence of triethyl ammine. The detailed strategy is summarized in Scheme 2. In di-nuclear copper compound [Cu₂L₂] **1**, both the metal centers possess a square planar environment and two Cu^{II} center are bridged by two alkoxy groups. The compound is stable in air at room temperature. The compound was characterized using IR, UV-Vis spectroscopy and single crystal X-ray crystallography.

The complex was initially characterized by IR spectroscopy. IR spectra of this complex displays all the characteristic bands of the coordinated (L)²⁻ ligand. One such prominent band appears at 1280 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu(\text{C-O/phenolate})$ stretching vibrations¹³. IR spectra of the complex has a couple of prominent bands appearing at ca. 1590 and 1506 cm⁻¹ regions, assignable to imine (C=N) group^{14,15}. IR spectrum of **1** also contains a strong band at 1088 cm⁻¹ due to the presence of bridging alkoxy groups¹⁶. The FTIR spectra indicate Cu₂O₂ ring vibration in 535 cm⁻¹ range¹⁷.

Description of crystal structure:

The molecular structure of **1** is shown in Fig. 2. It's important interatomic parameters are listed in Table 2. The complex crystallizes in monoclinic space group $P 2_1/n$.

Structural analysis reveals that compound **1** is a centrosymmetric di-nuclear entity where two Cu^{II} centers are bridged by two alkoxy O atoms of the ligand. Each Cu^{II} center in this di-nuclear complex is four coordinated and exist in square planar geometry. The coordination position around Cu^{II} centre is filled by imine nitrogen atom, phenoxo oxygen atom and alkoxy oxygen atom, all coming from doubly deprotonated tri-dentate ligand (L²⁻). Corresponding donor atoms around the Cu(2) center are, respectively, also coming exclusively from a second ligand molecule. Alkoxy oxygen atom from each ligand acts as a bridge between the copper centers. There is no hydrogen bonding interaction present within the molecule, as well as no ion dipole interaction is present. The bond distances of Cu-N (1.942 Å) and

Table 1. Summary of the crystallographic data for the complex **1**

Complex	1
Empirical formula	C ₂₆ H ₃₀ Cu ₂ N ₂ O ₄
Formula weight	561.60
T (K)	293(2)
λ (MoK _α), Å	0.71073
Crystal size (mm ³)	0.18x0.16x0.14
Space group	$P 2_1/n$
Crystal system	monoclinic
<i>a</i> (Å)	7.322(6)
<i>b</i> (Å)	9.938(9)
<i>c</i> (Å)	16.137(14)
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	1167.2(18)
<i>Z</i>	12
<i>D</i> _{calcd} (g cm ⁻³)	1.598
μ (mm ⁻¹)	1.859
<i>F</i> (000)	580
θ ranges (°)	(2.41°–31.87°)
Index ranges	–8 ≤ <i>h</i> ≤ 8 –11 ≤ <i>k</i> ≤ 11 –19 ≤ <i>l</i> ≤ 19
Reflections collected	8214
<i>R</i> _{int}	0.0509
Goodness of fit	1.141
No. of parameters	155
<i>R</i> ¹ (<i>F</i> _o), <i>wR</i> ² (<i>F</i> _o) (all data)	0.0356, 0.1031
Largest diff. peak, deepest hole, eÅ ⁻³	0.607, –0.696
^a <i>R</i> = $\sum F_o - F_c / \sum F_o $. ^b <i>wR</i> = $[\sum [w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2] / \sum w(F_o^2)^2]$	

Scheme 2. Schematic presentation of preparation of complex **1**.

Table 2. Selected bond distances (Å) and angles (deg) for **1**

Bond distance (Å)			
Cu01-O003	1.903(2)	Cu01-N004	1.942(3)
Cu01-O002	1.920(2)	Cu01-Cu01	3.034(2)
Cu01-O002	1.930(2)		
Bond angles (deg)			
O003-Cu01-O002	167.32(8)	O003-Cu01-O002	92.10(10)
O002-Cu01-O002	76.01(11)	O003-Cu01-N004	94.87(11)
O002-Cu01-N004	96.94(11)	O002-Cu01-N004	172.90(9)
O003-Cu01-Cu01	129.86(7)	O002-Cu01-Cu01	38.11(6)
O002-Cu01-Cu01	129.86(7)	N004-Cu01-Cu01	135.04(8)

Cu-O (1.903–1.930 Å) are all in the expected ranges^{18–20}. The intra molecular non bonding Cu(1)···Cu(1') separations is 3.034 Å²¹.

Electronic spectra:

The electronic spectra of the complex **1** have been recorded in methanol solution of the compound at room temperature and the data are summarized in the Experimental section. The electronic spectrum of the copper complex exhibits bands at 422 nm and 550 nm which can be assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_{1g}$ transitions^{22,23}. The complex also shows two intense bands in the near ultraviolet region due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and ligand (σ_L) \rightarrow metal (e_g) charge transfer transition²⁴.

Antibacterial activity:

Antibacterial activity of di-nuclear copper complex [Cu₂L₂] **1** dissolved in dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) has been monitored by agar-well diffusion method. Antibacterial activity of dimethyl sulphoxide and the free ligand (H₂L) were sepa-

Fig. 2. Molecular structure for complex **1**.

Fig. 3. Electronic absorption spectrum of complex **1** in MeOH.

rately also assayed. Here nutrient agar media was prepared and autoclaved under 121°C (15 lb) for 15 min for sterilization. Sterilized nutrient agar plates containing 30 ml of the media were inoculated with 500 µL each of *Aeromonas hydrophila*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus cereus* separately inside laminar flow chamber. In each plate two wells of 6 mm diameter were prepared using a sterile cork borer where one of them filled up with complex and other with DMSO as control. In the same way another set was prepared for ligand only. After 24 h of incubation at 37±1°C the zone of inhibition in agar plates were observed, measured and photographed. During the incubation period, the test solutions were diffused through nutrient agar and the growth of the inoculated microorganisms were affected. The zone of growth inhibition of each sample is given in Table 3.

Table 3. Antibacterial activity of the complex **1**, ligand (H₂L) and DMSO (inhibition zone in mm)

Test pathogen	Zone of inhibition (mm) against pathogenic bacteria		
	<i>A. hydrophila</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. cereus</i>
Complex 1	16	18	19
Ligand (H ₂ L)	14	0	0
DMSO	0	0	0

Concluding remarks

We have synthesized and characterized di-nuclear Cu^{II} complex [Cu₂L₂] **1** using tri-dentate Schiff base ligand with (O, N, O) donor site derived from the condensation of benzoylacetone and 3-amino propanol. The compound has

been authenticated by single crystal X-ray diffraction analysis. The core structure in **1** is centro symmetric binuclear alkoxo bridged Cu^{II} compound. Single crystal X-ray diffraction study reveals that in **1** the two four-coordinated copper atoms adopt a square planar geometry and two µ-alcoholic oxygen atoms bridge the two half-units forming a planar Cu₂O₂ core.

Antibacterial activity of di-nuclear Cu^{II} complex was observed by well plate technique. Antibacterial activity of complex **1** against *Aeromonas hydrophila*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus cereus* are considered to be valuable contribution to the researches on metal-based drugs field.

Supplementary data

CCDC 1860882 contains the supplementary crystallographic data for compound **1**. These data can be obtained free of charge via <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html>, or from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK; Fax: 44 1223-336-033; or E-mail: deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk.

Acknowledgement

Financial support received from Department of Science and Technology, Government of West Bengal, Kolkata (Project memo no. 1071(Sanc)/ST/P/S&T/15G-4/2015 dated 23.02.2016) is gratefully acknowledged. We are grateful for the instrumental support from the Department of Inorganic Chemistry, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science.

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